

recently receiving attention as catalyst¹⁻⁵. In this preliminary note we report the catalytic power of the dye, Rose Bengale.

Results and Discussion

To screen the dyes for catalytic power we measured the rate of oxygen evolution from a hydrogen peroxide solution with and without addition of the dye. Particular attention was paid that the final solutions were below pH 7 at which the rate of H₂O₂ decomposition is practically nil near room temperature. From spectrophotometric measurements it has been checked that the dye undergoes very little oxidation and the same dye is effective over many cycles of catalytic operations. From these experiments it has been found that among the dyes tried (listed below) only Rose Bengale and Erythrosin have fairly good catalytic power. It is to be noted that though Eosin and Iodo-eosin, are structurally similar to Rose Bengale yet their catalytic power in this decomposition reaction is nil and very little respectively.

List of dyes tested in the preliminary experiment

(1) Direct Sky Blue, (2) Azo carmine GX, (3) Rose Bengale, (4) Direct Brown, (5) Anthosin violet, (6) Biebrich Scarlet, (7) Direct Green B, (8) Chlorantine, (9) Chlorantine Fast Yellow (10) Tropaeolin O, (11) Eosin, (12) Iodo-eosin and (13) Erythrosin.

To have a clear idea of the catalytic power of Rose Bengale, this dye-catalysed decomposition of H₂O₂ was run at three different temperatures. The extent of reaction was measured by the volume of oxygen liberated in the gas burette attached to the reaction vessel. A control experiment (without adding the dye) was run side by side. The value of the rate constant (K_1) was determined from the slope of the plot of $\log(V_\infty - V_t)$ vs. time where V_∞ and V_t are respectively the initial total volume of oxygen in the H₂O₂ solution and that liberated after the interval of a certain time t . Energy of activation of the reaction was determined from the slope of the plot of $\log k_1$ vs. $1/T$ where T = temperature. Just to have an idea of the comparative efficiency of Rose Bengale we performed the same set of experiments using the conventional catalyst KI, whose results are included in the Table. The iodide ion is found to be about five times more efficient in equimolar concentration and to have somewhat lower energy of activation.

Mechanism. Most mechanisms of catalytic H₂O₂ decomposition involves an electron transfer mechanism involving oxidation-reduction cycles of the catalyst. Here such a mechanism is not possible because this dye is known to be irreversibly oxidised. This dye like most dyes of this group is devoid of colloidal properties. So we prefer the concept of a complex formation between the dye molecule and the H₂O₂. This intermediate is assumed to be rather unstable; the H₂O₂ moiety probably being under strain decomposes monomolecularly and the dye molecule undergoes such process again and again. However, we could not get any spectrophotometric evidence for the complex formation except that the shoulder at 517 nm tends to disappear

in presence of H₂O₂ leaving the main absorption peak (550 nm) almost unaffected.

TABLE 1

Conc. of H ₂ O ₂ (M)	Conc. of Catalyst (M)	Temp. °C	K ₁ (Dye) × 10 ⁶	K ₁ (Iodide) × 10 ⁶	E (Dye) KCal/mole	E (Iodide) KCal/mole
		32.5	4.55	2.43(32°C)		
2	3 × 10 ⁻⁴	38	7.52	3.18	13.14	11.5
		42	9.19	3.49		

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Reductive Dimerisation of Flavonoids : Syntheses of Some Biflavonoids

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METAL reduction reactions have been used since long to characterise flavonoids and various explanations have been offered for the coloured products formed in these reactions¹⁻⁶. Biflavonylidenes were found in the reductive acetylation⁷ products of flavonoids, contrary to the formation of only monomeric products as reported earlier. Jurd⁴ isolated crystalline biflavonylidenes, concluding thereby that the flavones unsubstituted in the 3 and 5 positions form dimeric bis-flavonylidenes under the conditions of reductive acetylation. Russel and Clark⁸ showed that the reduction of chalcones by zinc dust and alcoholic acid produced compounds which were qualitatively indistinguishable from the natural phlobatannins and flavpinacols. These reductive reactions usually yield complicated mixtures from which pure reduction products have rarely been separated and characterised.

During the present work 6,2'; 6,3' and 6,4'-dihydroxy flavanones were synthesised by acid cyclisation of the corresponding chalcones, which in turn were prepared by the condensation of the corresponding acetophenone derivatives and substituted benzaldehydes. On treatment with sodium amalgam in alcohol and subsequent acidification, these flavanones underwent reductive dimerisation yielding the corresponding biflavonoids [I (a), (b) and (c)], which could be isolated in the pure form from the reaction mixtures.

(I)

	R	R ₁	R ₂
(a)	OH	H	H
(b)	H	OH	H
(c)	H	H	OH

The m.p.s of I (a), (b) and (c) were respectively 138° (d.), 130° (d.) & 141° (d.). The elemental analysis & molecular weight determination of these biflavonoids were in agreement with the molecular formula C₃₀H₂₆O₈.

The absence of ketonic peak in the IR spectra indicated that the flavanones have been completely reduced. On complete methylation with diazomethane I (a) gave a product which analysed for four methoxyl groups (found OCH₃, 21.3%; calc. for C₃₀H₂₂O₄ (OCH₃)₄, 21.7%). The methyl ether of the biflavonoid I (a) still showed the absorption for hydroxyl group (ν_{max} 3,350 and 3,450 cm⁻¹) in the IR-spectrum, thereby indicating the presence of hydroxyl groups. The methyl ether of I (a) on acetylation gave a diacetate which analysed for two acetyl groups, confirming the presence of two hydroxyl groups. Similar results were obtained for the methyl ethers of I (b) and I (c) and these analysed for four methoxyl groups and formed diacetates.

The methyl ether of I (a) on treatment with sodium metaperiodate consumed one mole of periodate per mole of the compound. Thus the presence of a *cis*-biflavandiol linked at I-4, II-4 positions in I (a) has been established.

The reduction products I (a), (b) and (c) when methylated with dimethyl sulphate yielded the corresponding tetramethyl ethers but prolonged treatment (20 hr.) under these experimental conditions gave the cyclic carbonates, which were found to be identical with the product obtained from the reaction of these dimeric methyl ethers with ethylchloroformate and alkali.

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Alkaloids from *Elaeocarpus ganitrus* Roxb

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THE plant *Elaeocarpus ganitrus* (family *Elaeocarpaceae*) is commonly known as Rudraksha in India.

In the indigenous system of medicine the fruit is used in the treatment of epilepsy¹ and the seed is used in cardiac trouble². Earlier we reported³ some important pharmacological properties of the extracts of the seeds. e.g. pressure effect of long duration and marked positive inotropic effect on both intact and isolated mammalian hearts. The present paper deals with the isolation and characterization of two alkaloids from the leaves of the same plant.

From the ethanolic extract of the leaves of *E. ganitrus* two alkaloids have been isolated by preparative TLC over silica gel (Solvent system: benzene: chloroform: methanol=30:15:2, v/v).

The first alkaloid, C₁₆H₁₉NO₂, m. p., 81-82°, UV: λ_{max}^{EtOH} 320 nm. (ϵ 3200) and 253 nm (ϵ 8800), was characterized as (\pm) elaeocarpine by direct comparison (m. p., mixed m. p., TLC and GLC) with an authentic sample of (\pm) elaeocarpine⁴.

The second alkaloid, C₁₆H₁₉NO₂, m. p., 51-52°, UV: λ_{max}^{EtOH} 326 nm. (ϵ 3100) and 258 nm. (ϵ 9500), was characterized as (\pm) isoelaecarpine by direct comparison (m. p., mixed m. p., TLC and GLC) with an authentic sample of (\pm) isoelaecarpine⁴.

It may be mentioned here that (\pm) elaeocarpine and (\pm) isoelaecarpine are epimers. Their retention times (4.5 and 4.3 min. respectively) have been found to be different in GLC carried out under our experimental conditions (column 2%, S. E-33 nonpolar phase supported on 60-80 mesh gas chrom. Q and packed into a 6' x $\frac{1}{4}$ " stainless steel tube. The temperatures